

Cooling Down Earth with Heat Pumps

– Reducing CO2 Emissions by using Heat Pumps

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Abstract

Today there is overwhelming consensus about the existence of climate change. Humanity emits too much greenhouse gases into the atmosphere and that leads to constant warming of the earth's surface. This literature review deals with one aspect of reducing greenhouse gases: Heating in winter months and cooling in summer months of dwellings with the help of heat pumps. Heat pumps are an efficient technology and use the ambient energy to heat and cool rooms and to generate domestic hot water. Heat pumps run on electricity and are a perfect alternative to heating systems using fossil fuels. In addition, the review deals with the carbon footprint of heat pumps.

Keywords

Heat Pumps, Greenhouse Gas, CO2, Energy, Footprint

Introduction

In the 1970s, energy costs rose significantly due to the first oil crisis. This fact leads to a rethinking and the starting point for many researches on the efficient use of energy [1]. Electrification is one of the greatest contributions to curbing global warming. Theoretically, electricity that is produced with low carbon emissions can replace fossil fuels in many applications. Statistics [2] show that around half of the buildings in the European Union are heated with fossil-fuel heating systems. These heaters have an efficiency of 60% and less. Considering these facts, there is great potential to reduce greenhouse gases (GHG) and leave a small carbon footprint. With the signing of the Paris Agreement in 2015, many governments are working to reduce CO2 emissions and limit global warming to 2°C [3].

Methods

The method of this work is an analysis of published literature on the topic of CO2 reduction. The paper is focusing on two scientific studies, which are analyzed and provide information about the topic. The first paper "Lowering greenhouse gas emissions in the built environment by combining ground source heat pumps, photovoltaics and battery storage [3] deals with research on the impact of reducing CO2 emissions with the help of heat pumps, photovoltaic (PV) systems and battery energy storage systems (BESS) instead of fossil fuel heating systems. Heat pumps are powered by electricity, but the electricity generation mix is not beneficial for reducing emissions

from heat pumps. Heat pumps only cause fewer CO2 emissions if they are operated with photovoltaic systems or other alternative forms of energy. In addition, a battery storage system can reduce the peak demand for energy from the grid, thereby relieving the grid.

The second paper "Air-source heat pump carbon footprints: Hfc impacts and comparison to other heat sources"[4] deals with research on the carbon footprint of air source heat pumps and compared them to other heat sources. The goal of the analysis is to compile the carbon footprint of UK heat pumps over the whole life cycle. All greenhouse gases that arise during the production of raw materials, the use of energy in the heat pump and the disposal of components over the life of the heat pump are taken into account.

The authors [3] are using a techno-economic and environmental model to evaluate the impact on photovoltaic and storage on dwellings combined with a ground source heat pump (GSHP). They measured and collected data of the electricity consumption and photovoltaic electricity production of 16 dwellings. Also a battery storage model was developed which should lower the peak on the local grid and increase the photovoltaic self consumption. The lifetime of the analysis is set to 30-years based on the minimum expected lifetime of a dwelling. Service or replacement costs for components that are less than 30 years have also been taken into account.

Johnson [4] takes a look on the carbon footprint of heat pumps over the whole life cycle. To calculate the footprint for the analysis he focuses on the following aspects: composition of the air source heat

pump, inputs and outputs; raw materials production; electricity production and transmission; manufacture, installation and use of the air source heat pump; and disposal. For the individual areas, he took data from several sources and studies.

Results

The results for the first analysis [3] are splitted in two parts.

Self sufficiency ratio and grid impact

Fig. 1. Distributions of the (a) self-sufficiency ratio, (b) self-sufficiency ratio for specific functions, (c) import peak, (d) import peak to average ration (IPAR), (e) export peak, (f) eport peak to average ratio (EPAR); over a 30-years lifetime [3].

In Fig. 1. there are violin plots with different system combinations. The left violin plots always shows photovoltaic systems with and without ground source heat pumps. The rigth violin plots always shows photovoltaic systems with battery storage systems with and without ground source heat pumps. In plot (a) the self sufficiency ratio of PV and GSHP is lowest with a mean value of 25%. This rate can be increased to a mean value of 43% by using a battery storage system. The highest ratio with a mean value of 49% is the system with PV and BESS without GSHP. That is because the PV production is

highest in summer months while the highest GSHP consumption is during winter months.

Avoided life cycle ground source heat pump emissions

Fig. 2 shows violin plots that show the avoided and reduced life cycle emissions and the greenhouse gas payback periods (GHGPBP) through various system combinations. With a look at the elec. system perspective, the mean value of avoided GHG with a GSHP is 42,4%. With a PV system and a GSHP the avoided emissions have a mean value of 72,7%. A BESS system can not increase this value, because of the charge and discharge losses. The GHG reduction plot shows similary trends as the avoided GHG emissions. The GHG reduction is highest with a mean value of 80% with a GSHP and a PV system. With a required time of 2,5 years to offset the invested emissions is the GSHP lowest. All system combinations lying under 6 years GHGPBP.

On the right side there are the same plots with focus on dwelling perspective. The dwelling perspective only includes emissions avoided within a dwelling. In this case the perspective is not realistic as surplus PV electricity can be exported.

Fig. 2. Distributions of the (a) and (b) avoided life cycle emissions; (c) and (d) emission reduction; (e) and (f) greenhouse gas payback period (GHGPBP) from elec. system perspective and dwelling perspective [3].

As another result there is also an interesting diagram Fig. 3. which shows the daily electricity consumption with and without heat pumps over two years. In the diagram the energy consumption without HP is nearly constant with a mean value of 9kWh. This is because the systems used to heat,

cool and produce hot water are mostly inefficient. The energy consumption with HP and space heating is almost the same in the winter months as without. In the summer months, there is no need for heating, just cooling, and energy consumption drops to a low level. The water heating is also constantly at a low value throughout the year

Fig. 3. Daily energy consumption with and without heat pumps for heating, DHW, cooling and standby over two years [3].

The result of [4] shows the life time heat pump footprint base case average.

Fig. 4. Heat pump carbon footprint [4].

The largest part of the footprint is power with 81% followed by a significantly large value of 16% for refrigerant and the lowest percentage is the equipment with 2%.

In addition the footprint was also calculated for the unit kWh of heat delivered (kg CO₂e emitted per kWh of heat delivered) and compared to other heating systems. Fig. 5. shows a comparison of heat pumps to other fossil fuel heating systems.

Fig. 5. Footprints of heating systems with fuel or other power sources [4]. CNG (compressed natural gas); LPG (liquefied petroleum gas); LNG (liquefied natural gas)

The value for heat pumps with European efficiencies is around 0.205 kg CO₂e per kWh delivered, somewhat higher than for natural gas. The values for the other energy sources or forms go up to around 0.6 for harvested wood.

Conclusion

As shown in [3], GHG can be significantly avoided by using a GSHP in combination with a PV system for heating and cooling. The results in [4], shows the footprint for heat pumps is also not significantly higher than for natural gas heating systems. It can therefore be said that heat pumps in combination with a PV systems can significantly reduce CO₂ emissions and contribute to a more sustainable climate.

Literatur

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